
THE HANGING CLOUD OF MILITARY RULE AND THE CHALLENGE TO THE SURVIVAL OF DEMOCRACY IN NIGERIA.

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ABSTRACT.

Nigeria's effort at building strong democratic institution has continued to suffer series of setback due to the emergence of ethnic politics in the political system of the Country. This scenario has been made strong by the emerging elite group, referred to as political mafia. The emergence of the new political force made of retired military officers' conscious of holding political offices in disguise democratic setting; in collaboration with civilians aspiring for political offices has made it difficult for military coup to happen in Nigeria. Nevertheless, it has introduced a subversive political system that does not respect the rule of law. The direct consequences are election rigging, the selection and hoisting of unpopular candidates for elective positions in Nigeria. By hoisting unpopular candidates on the masses, the cause of Nation building has continued to suffer some setbacks, while the tenets of democratic government has remained mortgaged. When the incumbent President of Nigeria, President Ahmed Tinubu during his party campaign insisted that it was his turn to rule, election or no election, it was a clear statement that negates the principles of Democracy and the military mentality of obtaining power by force. This kind of politics cannot represent the interest of the generality of voters in a democratic setup. With respect to such utterances, Nigerian democracy cannot grow. Besides, if certain classes of people are not prevented from interfering on party politics, the electoral process in Nigeria will continue to be subverted. This action is necessary, because of the developmental nature of the democratic principles in Nigeria. Beside, military ethics brought to bear by military turned politicians in Nigerian politics, cannot accommodate democratic ethics, desired through free and fair

election. In effect, the act of merging the two political ideologies (Democracy and Militocracy together) has also given rise to leadership imposition, through Military supervised ballot boxes snatching and election rigging during election. Because the military wing of the Nigerian political system will always protect her own it is yet to be seen when free and fair election will begin in Nigeria. It is therefore the position of this paper, to suggest that Nigeria should adopt a process in the development of democratic principles that would accommodate her cultural and moral values, rather than encouraging money bag who are conscious to purchase political positions through monetary inducement and the application brutal force by the military turned politicians to obtain political power.

KEYWORDS: Military, Decree, Corruption, Leadership, Coup and Moral values.

INTRODUCTION.

Military intervention in any Country or government is bound to undermine the principles of democracy, Nigeria is no exception. Ojiakor aptly captured the consequences of military intervention, thus, ‘the bullet box has relegated the ballot box into obscurity and democracy was kicked brutally to fatal future’. In other words, every successful military coup in Nigeria has always drawn Nigeria several years backward in the development of democratic government. In that respect, the persistency Military incursion into Nigerian politics has left the Nation with little or no time to continue to nurture enduring democratic government.

In effect, In spite of several reasons always advanced each time military Junta took power, the solutions to Nigerian political problems seem to have been compounded through routine enactment of military decree. For instance, when General Ironsi took over after the first military coup of January 15, 1966, he stated by saying, ‘the Nigerian armed forces have been invited to form an interim government for the purpose of maintaining law and order’ The extent to which the law and order have been enforced need to be corroborated

However, the ethnicism which was introduced into Nigerian politics by civilians crept into Nigerian army after the counter coup of June 29th 1966. It should be recalled that northern element in the Military, did not give Ironsi the opportunity to right the perceived wrong of the past civilian government when they began to whip up ethnic sentiment against his government; in less than six months in power Ironsi was ousted. Gen. Gowon took over. In his maiden speech, Gowon stated as the reason for the counter coup, thus, ‘we consider it, our responsibility to lay foundation of a self sustaining political system which can stand a test of time’. However, the sit tight syndrome of the early African leaders of 1960s caught up with Gowon, even as he truncated every effort made at returning the country to the civilian, rule until he was removed from power through another military coup in Nigeria in 1975.

The danger portend by the sit tight military regime syndrome is that it prolonged the learning process of democratic system of government. Again, since military intervention often led to the suspension of the constitution of any country, and most time the killing of ousted civilian politicians overthrown by the military, this has also extended the learning process for sustainable democratic principles.

Considering the several reasons advanced for military intervention in Nigerian politics, it would become obvious to assert their failures. For instance, when Muritala Muhammed overthrew Gen. Gowon, he advanced as the reason, thus, ‘Nigeria has been left to drift. The situation if not arrested would inevitably have resulted in chaos and bloodshed’.

Gen. Buhari who overthrew Alhaji Shehu Shagari in December 1983 in his broadcast, stated as the reason for the coup, thus, 'We have dutifully intervened to save this Country from imminent collapse'. In fact, the economy of the Nation started collapsing during Buhari's regime in 1984 when he introduced structural adjustment programme (SAP), a situation that led Gen. Babangida to overthrow him. Babangida in reaction to the reason for overthrowing Gen. Buhari, stated, thus ...our human potential have been neglected. Our natural resources put to waste. A phenomenon of constant insecurity and overbearing uncertainty has become characteristics of our nation's existence⁶. The list of such is endless justification for coup with little or no remarkable achievements to the development and installation of sustainable democratic government by the Military who have rule Nigeria.

Although the incidence of Military coup has reduced in Nigeria, the reason is not that the military is no longer interested in Nigerian politics, but it is simply because the brand of politics (Milito-crazy) played in Nigeria today tends to have created a group of political gladiators who are ready to accommodate the interest of the military in and out of power. The noticeable danger as a result of that power politics has taken center stage. In respect to that, the enthronement of democratic rule in Nigeria has remained a furlong.

THE GENESIS OF MILITARY RULE IN NIGERIA.

The political crises in the Western Region of Nigeria of 1962 contributed for the first Military coup in Nigeria. This is in addition to the corrupt tendency of the civilian politicians. Generally, the following reasons as listed below formed the basis of the first Military coup in Nigeria.

The unabated crises was stoking when the 1963 census result were published. 'Before the 1963 census, the Ibos had believed themselves to be the most populace linguistic group in Nigeria... by rejecting it outcome of hand, a fresh stage was set for the resumption of anti-Ibo feeling'. The Northern People Congress scurrilous attacks on the Igbo people, in addition to the wild west political upheaval generated enough heat that would warrant military intervention in January 15, 1966.

Meanwhile, one would have requested to know how mere rejection of the census results would have translated to even Northern Nigerian owned Newspaper, to join the fray of attacking the Igbo people to the point of exceeding the bounds of both decency and reason by involving President Nnamdi Azikiwe in the tasteless witch-hunting that followed. In fact, taking the cue from the Northern Political leaders 'many natives Authorities did as well threatened the mass expulsion of the Igbo and the confiscation of their properties. The tirade that continued to be unleashed on the Igbo obviously created a picture of a country that lacked incentive to promote and sustain National Unity. To make the matter worse 'At the same time, the government of Western Nigeria which then had reached a sort of understanding with the regional government of Northern Nigeria on the census issue, also picked up on the anti-Igbo campaign'.

Apart from the census issues, several other factors including the utterances of some notable politicians, arson, political killing in the west, heated the polity the more. It thus, created obvious scenario for the military takeover of 15th January, 1966. It should be noted, before the coup, the personality clash between Chief Awolowo and his former deputy Chief Samuel Ladoke Akintola laid the foundation for the western regional political crises. In consequence, this problem started when Chief Awolowo gave up his position as the Premier of western region to Akintola to become the leader of the opposition in the federal parliament. According to his agreement with Chief Akintola, he was to double as the national leader of

the Action Group, but 'Chief Akintola '...did not like the idea, of Chief Awolowo still retaining the position of the leader. in addition, to even concede to Chief Awolowo the power of appointing Board member to the western region parastatals or even to nominate delegate to every important meeting of the party' was more than Akintola can chew. On the above conditions, Chief Akintola was not only embittered, but felt strongly against that. He felt, and rightly too, that 'as the Premier of Western region and leader of the Action Groups parliamentary party he was the right man to take decisions on such matters' ¹⁰. This disagreement marked the beginning of the political crises that would continue to dog the Western region until the military intervention in 1966.

Moreover, during the ensuing Political crises in the Western Region and by the time Chief Akintola had travelled overseas on Economic mission after the constitution of the board members, the quarrel has become noticed as he had tactically replaced Chief Awolowo's men who ought to have travelled with him. Although Chief Awolowo overlooked his action, but the damage has already been done. The second open quarrel between the twosomes was when Chief Akintola refused to renew the appointments of board members who were loyal to Awolowo. In order to display total control of his leadership over the Action Group, Chief Akintola equally put to a stop 'huge loans his government and its controlled organizations had been making to certain individual Action Group leaders' ¹¹. These and many other issues stoked the beam of fire that were to sustain the western regional Political crises in the Western Region until Akintola was killed in the military coup of January 15, 1966.

On the part of the central government, since Chief Awolowo was the leader of the opposition at the Federal house, Alhaji Abubakar Tafawa Balewa the Prime Minister and his party found an opportunity to capitalize on the quarrel between Chief Akintola and Chief Awolowo to create more problems before the declaration state of emergency in the Western Region. It should be noted, that Akintola in his bid to become the Premier of the Western Region had formed the Nigerian National Democratic Party (NNDP) in order to actualize his ambition.

What led to the formation of NNDP was because of Chief Akintola anti Party activities. When he was replaced with Chief Adegbenro he refused to step down, even as he hurriedly rushed to Alhaji Tafawa Balewa to refrain the Governor of the region from calling Alhaji Adegbenro to form a regional government. Chief Akintola's refusal to vacate office aggravated the political crisis in the region. It should be noted that, because the central government was key beneficiary to the crisis in the region no serious effort was made to address the Western Nigeria Political crisis once and for all.

In effect, the massive protest that greeted the altercation for the Premiership seat of Western Region led to serious arson, killing and destruction of properties. The unabated crisis all combined to force the government of Alhaji Tafawa Balewa to declare state of emergency in the region just to create interregnum in order to return Akintola to power through the back door.

During the emergency period Dr. Moses Majekodunmi the federal minister of Health was appointed the administrator of the volatile Western Region. Majekodunmi's rule during the emergency period was firm and focused, and sanity was restored within a short period. At the end of the emergency rule Akintola was restored as the Premier of the western region. His re-appointment led to the re-opening of the old political wound. To aggravates the matter; When Akintola finally left the Action Group to NNDP the Political gulf between the Action Group and Akintola widened. It was as a result of the ensued war, in addition to the federal

government meddlesome in Western Region's election results of 1964 that created the scenario for the military takeover in January 15th 1966.

On the heels of the election rigging to favor Akintola's New Party, was the allegation of 'treason charge against Chief Awolowo and some top Party leaders of Action Group'¹². This is in addition to the accusation of mis-management of the public fund earlier on leveled against Awolowo by Akintola. This was brewing when Coker's commission was constituted by the federal government to investigate Awolowo and co., on treason charges.

The Coker commission of Inquiry which lasted from November 12, 1962 to June 27, 1963 later found Chief Awolowo guilty of all the treason charges and while he was sentenced to ten years imprisonment with hard labour, Chief Enahoro a chieftain of Action Group was also found guilty of all charges and sentenced to fifteen years imprisonment with hard labour. Other accused were also sentenced to some years of imprisonments.

From the research one of the key underlining reason that have prompted the Military intervention was due to the political impunity of the Northern People's Congress leadership. By suspended and recalling Chief Akintola who had been responsible for the sustained political crises in the Western Region, It was thus, beyond what any reasonable and passionate Military can bear.

The state of political confusion continued all over the Nation except in the North. This thus became a glaring deliberate act to promote the policy of divide and rule under the superintendency of Alhaji Tafawa Balewa of the Northern People's Congress. Initially, when Chief Akintola was returned to power after the state of emergency, he went into a temporary alliance with NCNC by appointing one of its leaders in the West Chief Fani-Kayode as his deputy. This alliance would subsequently proved that Chief Akintola used the strategy to buy time in order to achieve two purposes, firstly to use the alliance to straighten the position of his new party in the Western Region, and secondly, to use it to destabilize the Action Group in the West. Against this backdrop some well meaning Nigeria at the time, had started complained bitterly about the political desperation of Chief Akintola and co travellers in the West, and the danger it portend, but all in vain.

In fact, in 1966 before the military coup of January, a leading Religious and Political leader from the Northern region had 'complained that the political situation in Nigeria was steadily deteriorating and that if nothing was done immediately to bring the Palavar in Western Nigeria under control, there would be no telling of what would happen'¹³. From the above account, it was obvious that those who ought to have salvage the situation remained aloof until the Military intervened in January 15, 1966 when the situation has become hapless.

Alhaji Tafawa Balewa the Prime Minister at that time should share in the blame. As a leader; he lacked the charisma and tended to have enjoyed the Western Regional political crises by supporting less popular leader like Chief Akintola just for the sake of promoting the interest of his own Party the NPC. He accepted the massively rigged census figures that favored the North to the detriment of National Unity. He looked the other when Western Regional election was rigged to the detriment of opposition Parties.

The Western Region political leaders' action or inaction also precipitated the crises. They allowed their conscience to venerate selfish interest. The Federal of Nigeria was partisan, therefore should equally share in the blame by encouraging selfish interest of certain individuals to undermine the collective goods, and also by inciting Akintola to form a new

Political Party in the West it was obvious that the AG supporters would be drawn to war with the supporters of Chief Awolowo.

Chief Akintola was desperate to drag the Yoruba to the central government by hook and crook according to him, for the sake of just to participate in the sharing of the national cake. His sense of judgment beclouded him from seeing the reality and the danger of trying to hoist the selfish ambition of his few cohorts on the well being of the majority. The political thuggery, killing and wanton destruction of properties of the 1960s were perpetrated by this rapacious ambition.

When the military finally struck in January 15, 1966, they targeted corrupt leaders, those that had worked against the unity of the country and over ambitious leaders who have introduced religion into Nigerian politics. It was therefore not surprise those eliminated aptly fit the specifications listed above. In the words of one of the five majors that executed the coup, Major Kaduna Nzeogwu, he stated during an interview, thus, 'we must see that they do not come back'. Lt.Col. Hassan Usman Katsina, the governor of Northern region, while address the public stated, thus, 'Everyone must realize that we are one nation irrespective of the tribe from which each of us originated from our experiences in the past have shown the political parties had not worked for the common good but for sectional interest'. These are among the reasons for January 15, 1966 military intervention. The joy that greeted the military takeover was beyond description.

Barely six months after this coup, there was a counter-coup. The counter-coup of July 29, 1966 assumed tribal colouration because the young army officers that prosecuted it came from a particular region and were brainwashed to believe that the first coup was targeted against a particular tribe, so the counter-coup came with vengeance. This obviously deepened the tribal sentiment and contributed to drift the nation apart. On the account of the above statement, the nation is yet to recover from the rascality of the counter-coup.

THE CONSEQUENCES OF THE MILITARY RULE IN NIGERIAN POLITICAL DEVELOPMENT.

The counter-coup of June 29, 1966 was not one carried out to restore cohesion to political quagmire of 1966 midwife by the western region of Nigeria, but was strictly carried out on sentiment, and such could not have sustain National Unity. In effect, the aftermath of that coup has continued to hunt the Nation. It is not an understatement to say that, the counter-coup of 1966 was carried out by young inexperienced army officers who lacked what it takes to build national unity, and whose quest to be counted was their motivated factor. The coup thus has it focus to restore the pride of the Northern politicians which was anchored to retain political power for life. The fear of domination expressed by other regions (Western and Northern regions) was reinforced when Lt. Colonel Yakubu Gowon was appointed after the counter coup.

The counter-coup of July 29, 1966 and systematic attacks on Igbo people all over the place except in the south east continued unabated until the outbreak of the civil war. The war lasted for almost three years and seemed to have clearly shown that the Nation was not willing to live in unity when Chief Obafemi Awolowo introduced and economic policies targeted to destroy the economic strength of the Igbo people. This is also to demonstrate the fact that, military always intervened with set-targets, and such targets as the case may be with Nigeria are usually for personal enrichment and on vindictive mission. It is on record that during the regime of General Gowon, 'in 1970 total production of crude oil rose from 5,100 in 1958 to

396 million barrels, rising further to 634 million in 1972, and 823 million in 1974'. However, the inability of the Head of state to diversify the economy during the boom times as a result of institutionalized corrupt system in Nigeria denied her the opportunity to become industrial giant. As a result of this and many other actions taken then, Gowon's government is known to have sustained the corrupt administration the first republic government was accused of. This assertion has been supported Falola, thus, 'the oil boom also resulted in widespread corruption, which was responsible to the development of a rentier state in Nigeria'¹⁷. It was not out of place when his government was overthrown in a bloodless coup in 1975, more so when he reneged to initiate the transition to civil rule as promised.

It should also be noted that General Gowon's appointed as the Head of state was shredded in corruption too. Unlike the January 15, 1966 coup where Gen. Ironsi's appointment was on merit, Gowon's was spurious and questionable, to that effect; the counter coup of July 29, 1966 was clearly executed to implement ethnic agenda. Even when the eastern region's military Governor Col. Ojukwu had insisted that the status quo be maintained by appointing the most senior instead of Lt. Col. Gowon, while the Western and Northern saw nothing wrong in Gowon's appointment and continued to hype ethnicism in a very important circle of unity in Nigeria, the Military.

When Gowon was finally removed from power in 1975, Gen. Muritala Muhammed who assumed power tried vigorously to clear the mess left by Gowon. This is reflective in his maiden broadcast when he stated, 'the failure to hand over power to civilian government as promised; and the exclusion of some key battle field officers from corridors of power and patronage'¹⁸ in formed the reason while the Military intervened. From the above account, the second point raised by the coupist as being responsible for the coup actually bothered on gratification, this is what obtains in military rule over the years.

The promise to address the corrupt act which the Military often claimed to have been the reason for takeover could be seen to be lie. Unfortunately, Gen. Muritala Muhammed's government was toppled in less than six months by Lt. Col. Buka Suka Dimka and Gen. Iliya in a botched military coup. The chains of coup plots within ten years after the civil war seemed to be deliberate acts perpetrated to please and appreciate the Generals who participated during the civil war. This could be proved considering the tribes of the officers appointed to juicy positions during the Military regime.

When General Olusegun Obasanjo took over after the assassination of his boss Muritala Muhammed in 1976, he continued with laid down policies of his boss. More importantly, he initiated the transition to the civilian rule and succeeded in handing over power to the civilian in October 1, 1979. In Election that was conducted Alhaji Shehu Shagari of NPN was elected the President. Again the military taste for power came to bear, when in December 31, 1983 Alhaji Shehu Shagari was over thrown by Gen. Buhari. The regularity of the military incursion into Nigerian politics appeared to have been motivated by two factors, namely:

- (i) When the positions of Northern political leaders appeared to be threatened by Southern Politicians.
- (ii) When there are tough political policies that will disfavor the North eg. Power shift and the reservation of certain sensitive Political Positions for the southern Politicians.

On the account of the above information, it appeared almost all successful military coups are the one with the full support of the North, and the botched ones equally appeared to have

been thwarted by the Northern soldiers. All the coups in Nigeria have never been without what appeared to be genuine reason for intervention, but time and space has always ended in exposing the military regime as the worst. For instance, when Gen. Buhari took over after President Shehu Shagari was overthrown, he claimed 'that the reason he and cohorts took the realm of power by military means was to combat indiscipline and corruption'¹⁹.

He introduced 'war against indiscipline' as a camouflage to his highly corrupt administration. Obviously the intervention was to deny a very popular candidate Dr. Alex Ekwueme an Igbo from the Southern Nigeria the opportunity of taking over from at the end of Shehu Shagari's tenure as contains in the Party's constitution. Gen. Buhari was later overthrown by yet another Northern in the Person of Gen. Ibrahim Babangida. It was during Gen. Babangida's regime that more states and local government councils were created. The North was favoured in this exercise to the point that Kano State alone with 44 local councils equaled almost three states from the East combined. By this creation the North was politically empowered more than the South.

Generals Babangida and Buhari's administration also introduced policies that subjected the masses to untold hardship. Some of these policies which were implemented on the instance of International Monetary Fund included the structural adjustment program (SAP). By implementing, this program, IMF effectively usurped the Country's sovereign rights to home groomed Economic Policy, and self determination in the choice of Economic Policy and implementation for the wellbeing of its citizens. Babangida's administration clearly exposed the Military's lack of knowledge of international politics, as he allowed the Nation's domestic and foreign policies to be dictated by the world financial institution and its western allies. According to Onwudiwe, 'the IMF Conditionality were said to have rendered the Country as a subservient nation, to western capitalist economy'.

The sit tight syndrome which has become the nemesis of military leaders almost caught up with Gen. Babangida, when he truncated the transition to civilian rule. He conducted an election, but when his ordained Northern candidate Alhaji Bashir Tofa was defeated by southern candidate in the person of Chief Moshod Abiola, he quickly annulled the election. That incidence brought the Country to the brink of another civil war. It was also in the heat of the annulment of that election result that another military officer named Gen. Sani Abacha took over power in a well planned bloodless coup that saw the removal of interim leader, Mr. Ernest Shonekon.

Gen. Abacha whose greed for power was not hidden, attempted to elongate his tenure too, by refusing to normalize the election results that declared Abiola winner. However, the mysterious death of the two contenders (Gen. Abacha and Chief Abiola within a space of one week) saw the emergence Gen. Abdulsalami Abubakar as the new Head of State.

From records, Military has never been a better alternative to civilian rule in Nigeria because both had the same aspiration of corrupt tendency, in addition to the hoist of ethnic sentiment. After Nigerian independence, Dr. Nnamdi Azikiwe has requested for the abolition of the regional political structure in preference to strong central government. Gen. Aguiyi Ironsi that took power in January 1966 lent his support, when he promulgated the decree 34 for the sake of promoting the national unity, but the North was indisposed to such policy due their fear of Igbo domination. Gen. Ironsi was later overthrown by Military element from the Northern Nigeria in June 1966, to the consternation of everybody.

Gen. Gowon a Northern army officer took over from Aguiyi Ironsi. It was strange to every Nigerian when he made the central government very strong on assumption of office. According to Onwudiwe, 'the military government in Nigeria therefore used the instrumentality of might to impose northern authority over Nigeria political system'. The military adventure into politics in Nigeria is therefore an aberration to Nigeria Unity, as the North saw their control over the military as the means of retaining power for a long time.

DEMOCRACY AND MILITARY REGIME IN NIGERIA: THE CONSEQUENCES.

The failure of the democratic system of government in Nigeria has created the opportunity for Military intervention in Nigerian politics. The regularity of the Military incursion has however slowed down because this system of government is becoming unpopular in Nigeria. The danger it portends is that Nigeria has created Military institution formation that is inept to duties. Where ever the Military is in power the constitution of the Nation is usually suspended and leadership is by decree enacted without wider consultation inimical with democratic government. Since the rule of law seized to exist in Military government autocratic rule and Anarchy often augment totalitarianism .According to Howard Handleman 'if civilian are willing to accept democracy as a value, it is hard to see how a professional military would be drawn into politics'. Since independence Nigeria political leaders have continued to experiment with some political system to no avail. The reason is not farfetched the democratic values have not been fully incorporated into the Nation's political system. Again political scientists have identified two factors responsible for military intervention in politics as it relate with developing Countries. They pointed out the internal characteristics of the armed forces themselves and the political environment in which the military operates especially when civilian government is weak, as it were with civilian government in Nigeria. Military intervened in politics when they lack ideological orientations. So when military is well organized, adequately educated, strong, internally organized, the probability of military involvement in politics will be minimized.

Since democratic ideology is basically to implement people oriented policies, military government tend to restrict that, for instance, 'military expenditures are frequently higher than their Country can afford, thereby reducing badly needed social and economic investment'. Nigeria has not fought an international war in decades, but has spent fortunes on the military. In a democratic system of government where certain measure of freedom is granted such could negate military principle. For instance, 'any form of disorder violates their hierarchical view of society'. In that respect, human right abuse is recorded more during the military regime than the civilian.

With all these, obviously the army has failed to install stability which they often claimed to have come to restore. Military intervention into Nigerian politics has disconnected some military personnel from the core professionalism. As a matter of fact, quite a number of retired military officers have wasted no time to join politics because of the new passion and attraction often expressed for the highly corrupt and dirty Nigerian politics. Military out of power (retired Military officers) intervention in Nigerian politics is being made strong due to synergy built between military in power and military out of power in relationship with the civilians in power and civilians out of power strategy of politics in Nigeria. This political arrangement is a new development that has continued to undermine democratic principles in Nigerian political system. It has as well minimized the incidence of military coup in Nigeria. Basically that is the reason why the abuse of power has not been reciprocated by military takeover in Nigeria.

Military involvement in Nigerian politics has created a class of civilian collaborators whose aim is on how to use state apparatus to sustain corrupt practices. President Obasanjo and Gen. Muhammadu Buhari have enjoyed such collaboration. The two persons mentioned above were once military Head of State whose act of benevolence while with the civilian collaborators were rewarded after they retired from army and join politics. For eight years they were elected to serve as the civilian Presidents. President Obasanjo was elected under the people's Democratic Party (PDP), while Buhari was elected under All Progressives Congress (APC).

This new arrangement will continue to sustain corrupt political system for every long time. In addition, in order to sustain this trend, Nigeria military has evolved a kind of political system institutionalized in character by training. Sometimes the military personnel enroll in specialized seminars with civilian leaders (National Institute of Strategic Studies), through this they have established links with the politicians, business people and academic. The situation is such that if any of the civilian collaborators are elected to political positions they will have capable hands from the military who would quit the military constituency to join party politics, and thus create the conducive political leverage for sustainable corrupt practices. In any case, if at any time the military seizes power, 'they are likely to govern collectively rather than vest authority in the hands of a single leader'. In other words, institutionalized regime not democratic rule is gradually taking root in Nigeria due to long period of Military rule.

CONCLUSION

Military intervention in Nigeria politics has not only undermined the growth and development of Democracy in Nigeria, but also has thwarted the process of Nation-building. This is because military professionalism has been mortgaged with inordinate quest for political power in the military circle. In January 15, 1966 Nigeria experienced her first Military coup. Considering the political situation prior to the coup, the intervention could be justified. This is because six years after the Nation's independence, the civilian government lacks of political savvy drove the Country to the precipice. The inability of the political gladiators to effectively navigate the Nation's Socio-Political and Economic terrain was made worse by the Ethnic Politics that stood very tall at the threshold of Political breakthrough.

Ethnic politics beclouded the senses of so called National leaders, to the point that mutual trust among the political elites was mortgaged for selfish interest anchored on the promotion of Ethnic Politics. Because the political elites were power drunk, free and fair election could not be guaranteed, even the census exercise conducted was marred by figures inflation. As a result of the corrupt tendencies of the political elites, the principles of Democracy were flagrantly abused. It was however the personality clash between Chief Obafemi Awolowo and his former Deputy Chief Ladoke Akintola that broke the Carmel's back.

The military intervention in January 15, 1966 was necessitated by the political crises of a region that has experienced more political killing, vandalism, arson, state of emergency etc. than the other three. It was thus, a great relief when in January 15, 1966; the Military struck to end the political destruction that would have engulf the entire Nation if left unchecked. The euphoria that greeted the first military coup was a clear demonstration of people's acknowledgement of the failure of the civilians rule. The Military intervention which was swift served the masses from the apprehension resulting from the political brouhaha of the Western region.

From the above account, it was obvious that the weaknesses of the civilian government adversely aided the military intervention. This was aptly captured in Finer's theory in Ngozi Ojiakor who stated that 'the military intervene in politics according to the levels of political culture, which were determined by the strength or weakness attached to civilian institution'²⁷. Obviously the above statement clearly said the fact. However, the second military coup of July 29, 1966 which was a counter-coup was actually on vindictive mission carried out to reposition the Northern region on political dominance of the country. Ethnic politics that marred the civilian government was speedily restored with vengeful antecedent. In fact, what Major Kaduna Nzeogwu led coup had attempted to achieve was obliterated within a twinkle of an eye.

If actually the coup leaders of the first military coup in Nigeria carried out the coup in order to remove the corrupt politicians from power, they did well in sparing the lives of those, whose track records in Economic and Political development at the time was glaring. Killing them to assuage Ethnic feelings as the directors of the counter coup have envisaged should not have been for the best interest of the Nation. It was therefore the unfounded fear of the domination of the Igbo people that led to the second military coup of July 29, 1966. In effect and certainly too, whatever the Nation has achieved in terms of cohesiveness was destroyed by the second military coup.

The second Military coup created a political group who sustained corrupt tendencies, and not only married but also imposed Islamic religion with politics. This has continued to undermine the development of the democratic government. Chinweizu in support of the above argument, stated, thus, 'Nigeria is a torn Country, a Country torn between two irreconcilable versions of what it should become, they are the Feudal-theocracy version and the secular-democracy version'. The danger portend by this approach to the growth of the democratic government, is that the military headed at one time by Muslims have laid the foundation of a political system of government in Nigeria that would always be influenced by Islamic religion, and this is against the development of democracy. The rate at which the military still influenced Political equation in Nigeria is alarming. Military in power, whether retired or active, is not to nurture democracy but to perpetrate anarchy by using political positions to sustain gratification.

How can one explain Gen. Jeremiah Useni (rtd), who was involved in the counter-coup of June 29, 1966 to good enough as to participate in the last Gubernatorial Election of his home State Plateau. Even when he had retired, Gen. Useni was still desperate for political power. This is a trait often exhibited by Military in most third world Countries. By training, Military are not prepared for more tolerant democratic system of government, they lack the patience. In other words, in most third world countries their involvement in party politics cannot grow democratic government. The military interventions whether as retired or active have continued to portray anarchy, totalitarian and despotic tendencies, which are of course, against the tenets of democratic government.

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